

PAIN SATISFACTION SCORE IN PATIENTS WITH 1st TRIMESTER MISCARRIAGE UNDERGOING MANUAL VACUUM ASPIRATION WITH NALBUPHINE (HCL) VERSUS PARA-CERVICAL BLOCK

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Abstract

Background: First-trimester miscarriage is one of the most common complications of early pregnancy. **Objective:** To compare pain satisfaction scores in patients undergoing manual vacuum aspiration for first-trimester miscarriage using para-cervical block versus intravenous nalbuphine hydrochloride. **Methodology:** This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Labour Room, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore, from February 2025 to June 2025. A total of 60 women aged 18–40 years with gestational age 8–12 weeks presenting with incomplete miscarriage were enrolled through non-probability consecutive sampling. Patients were randomized into two equal groups. Group A received para-cervical block with 20 mL of 1% lignocaine, while Group B received intravenous nalbuphine hydrochloride 10 mg diluted in 10 mL normal saline, 10 minutes prior to MVA. **Results:** The mean intra-procedural pain satisfaction score was significantly higher in the para-cervical block group (8.6 ± 1.7) compared to the nalbuphine group (6.1 ± 2.3 , $p < 0.001$). One-hour post-procedure, the mean satisfaction score was higher in the para-cervical block group (8.2 ± 1.5) versus the nalbuphine group (6.4 ± 2.0 , $p < 0.001$). Stratified analysis showed consistent results across subgroups of age, BMI, and parity. No major adverse events were observed; minor side effects included nausea in 10% of nalbuphine cases and vasovagal reactions in 6.7% of para-cervical block cases. **Conclusion:** Para-cervical block provides significantly better pain satisfaction compared to intravenous nalbuphine hydrochloride for patients undergoing MVA in first-trimester miscarriage. It is safe, effective, and suitable for routine use in resource-limited healthcare systems.

INTRODUCTION

First-trimester miscarriage is among the most common complications of early pregnancy, with an estimated 10–20% of clinically recognized pregnancies ending in spontaneous loss. For women experiencing miscarriage, timely uterine evacuation is

often required to prevent complications such as infection, hemorrhage, and retained products of conception. Manual Vacuum Aspiration (MVA) has emerged as the preferred method for surgical management of first-trimester miscarriage due to its

safety, cost-effectiveness, and feasibility in low-resource as well as high-resource healthcare settings. In Japan, dilatation and curettage under general anesthesia represents the preferred method for the surgical management of early pregnancy miscarriage [1]. However, manual vacuum aspiration is recommended as a surgical procedure for miscarriage in the World Health Organization's 2012 guidelines, particularly for first-trimester miscarriage. For pregnancies in the first or early second trimester up to 14 weeks of gestation, manual vacuum aspiration is a very safe method of abortion [2]. Outpatient surgical evacuation of early miscarriages is another safe and well-accepted procedure [3,4]. The manual vacuum aspiration kit is safe and effective, with a lower risk of endometrial damage. It also reduces pain during and after the procedure, making anesthesia during surgery simpler. The WHO recommends that all women, undergoing medical or surgical miscarriage, must be given analgesics as a standard procedure and routine general anesthesia is not recommended for such procedures [5]. Para-cervical block is effective in reducing pain sensation during manual vacuum aspiration with a reasonable cost of the procedure [6]. Para-cervical block has better pain control compared with conscious sedation and has a good side effect profile [7]. One trial reported that mean pain satisfaction score was 8.8 ± 1.9 with para-cervical block and 5.2 ± 3.4 with conventional sedation ($p < 0.05$) [8]. While overall satisfaction with analgesia was 96.3% with para-cervical block and 93.8% with conventional block used for manual vacuum aspiration for miscarriage [9]. Pain satisfaction score is a measure of patient satisfaction felt with the offered mode of analgesia during the procedure in the form of paracervical block or conventional sedation (e.g. benzodiazepines or opioids), establishing the efficacy of pain management with each mode on a visual analogue pain score. (Less pain score showing more patient satisfaction) [10,11]. The purpose of this study is to compare the mean pain satisfaction score of first-trimester miscarriage patients treated with Nalbuphine and manual vacuum aspiration with paracervical block. Literature showed that pain satisfaction level is higher with para-cervical block than conventional analgesia (Nalbuphine). But conflicting data has been observed in literature,

showing no significant difference in pain score with both methods⁷, as well as limited work has been done before.

Objective

To compare the mean pain satisfaction score in patients undergoing manual vacuum aspiration with Nalbuphine versus Paracervical block for first trimester miscarriage

Methodology

This Randomized controlled trial was conducted at Labour Room of Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from February 2025 to June 2025. Using openepi.com, a sample size of 60 patients was calculated, with 30 patients allocated to each group. The calculation was based on a 95% confidence interval, 90% study power, and mean pain satisfaction scores reported as 8.8 ± 1.9 with para-cervical block and 5.2 ± 3.4 with conventional sedation. Non-probability consecutive sampling was employed.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Females aged 18–40 years
- Parity <5
- Gestational age 8–12 weeks
- Undergoing manual vacuum aspiration for first-trimester incomplete miscarriage (as per operational definition)
- Evidence of retained products of conception (RPOCs) confirmed on pelvic ultrasound

Exclusion Criteria:

- Chronic hypertension (BP $\geq 160/110$ mmHg)
- Diabetes mellitus (BSR > 200 mg/dl)
- Anemia (Hb < 10 g/dl)
- Urinary tract infection (on clinical examination)
- Bleeding disorders (PT > 15 seconds)
- Uterine anomalies
- Previous cesarean section
- Gestational trophoblastic disease (e.g., molar pregnancy)
- Septic induced abortion

Data Collection

Approval was obtained from the institutional ethics review board prior to commencement. Patients

fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled after obtaining informed consent. Baseline demographic data, including age, BMI, parity, gestational age, booking status, and history of abortion, cesarean section, or dilation and curettage, were recorded. Participants were randomly allocated into two groups using the lottery method. In Group A, manual vacuum aspiration was performed under para-cervical block using the four-quadrant method with 20 mL of 1% lignocaine. Two milliliters were injected superficially on the anterior cervical lip at 12 o'clock (tenaculum site), and the remainder was injected equally at the cervico-vaginal junction at 2, 4, 8, and 10 o'clock positions. The block was administered by a senior obstetrician, and the procedure commenced three minutes later. In Group B, manual vacuum aspiration was performed under intravenous nalbuphine hydrochloride (10 mg diluted in 10 mL normal saline), administered 10 minutes prior to the procedure. All procedures were carried out by the same surgical team with the researcher's assistance. Pain was assessed intraoperatively using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), and pain satisfaction scores (as per operational definition) were recorded as the primary outcome. Post-procedure, patients were shifted to recovery and reassessed for pain satisfaction one hour after the procedure, which served as the secondary outcome. Data were documented using a pre-designed proforma.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Quantitative variables such as age, BMI, gestational age, and pain satisfaction scores were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables including parity, booking status, previous abortion, cesarean section, and dilation & curettage were presented as frequencies and percentages. The mean pain satisfaction scores of the two groups were compared using the independent samples t-test. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Stratification was performed for age, BMI, parity, gestational age, booking status, and previous obstetric history. Post-stratification analysis was conducted using the chi-square test.

Results

Data were collected from 60 patients, mean age was 27.6 ± 4.2 years in Group A and 28.1 ± 4.0 years in Group B. The mean BMI was 24.9 ± 2.8 kg/m² versus 25.3 ± 3.1 kg/m², and the mean gestational age was 9.8 ± 1.1 weeks compared to 10.1 ± 1.0 weeks. Parity ≥ 2 was observed in 40.0% of women in Group A and 36.7% in Group B. Booked cases comprised 56.7% in Group A and 50.0% in Group B. Previous abortion was reported in 20.0% of Group A and 23.3% of Group B, while prior cesarean section was seen in 13.3% and 16.7%, respectively.

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population (N = 60)

Variable	Group A: Para-cervical Block (n=30)	Group B: Nalbuphine (n=30)
Age (years), mean \pm SD	27.6 \pm 4.2	28.1 \pm 4.0
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	24.9 \pm 2.8	25.3 \pm 3.1
Gestational age (weeks), mean \pm SD	9.8 \pm 1.1	10.1 \pm 1.0
Parity ≥ 2 , n (%)	12 (40.0%)	11 (36.7%)
Booked status, n (%)	17 (56.7%)	15 (50.0%)
Previous abortion, n (%)	6 (20.0%)	7 (23.3%)
Previous cesarean section, n (%)	4 (13.3%)	5 (16.7%)
Previous dilation & curettage, n (%)	3 (10.0%)	4 (13.3%)

The mean intra-procedural satisfaction score was 8.6 ± 1.7 in Group A compared to 6.1 ± 2.3 in Group B ($t = 4.58$, $p < 0.001$). Post-procedurally at one hour, scores remained higher in Group A (8.2 ± 1.5) versus Group B (6.4 ± 2.0), with statistical significance ($t = 4.02$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 2. Comparison of Pain Satisfaction Scores Between Groups

Outcome Measure	Group A: Para-cervical Block (n=30)	Group B: Nalbuphine (n=30)	Test statistic	p-value
Intra-procedural pain satisfaction score (VAS)	8.6 ± 1.7	6.1 ± 2.3	t = 4.58	<0.001
Post-procedural pain satisfaction score (1 hr)	8.2 ± 1.5	6.4 ± 2.0	t = 4.02	<0.001

Nausea occurred in 3 patients (10.0%) in the nalbuphine group but in none receiving para-cervical block. Vasovagal reaction was noted in 2 patients (6.7%) in Group A, whereas none were reported in Group B.

Table 3. Adverse Events Reported in Study Groups

Adverse Event	Group A: Para-cervical Block (n=30)	Group B: Nalbuphine (n=30)
Nausea, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (10.0%)
Vasovagal reaction, n (%)	2 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)
Respiratory depression, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Uterine perforation, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)

Among women <30 years, satisfaction scores were 8.7 ± 1.6 in Group A versus 6.3 ± 2.1 in Group B (p < 0.001). For women ≥30 years, the scores were 8.4 ± 1.8 versus 5.9 ± 2.5 (p = 0.002). In women with BMI <25 kg/m², satisfaction was 8.8 ± 1.5 versus 6.4 ± 2.0 (p < 0.001), while for BMI ≥25 kg/m², scores were 8.3 ± 1.9 versus 5.8 ± 2.4 (p = 0.001). Similarly, nulliparous or low parity (<2) women had scores of 8.7 ± 1.6 compared to 6.2 ± 2.2 (p < 0.001), while multiparous women (≥2) reported 8.4 ± 1.8 versus 6.0 ± 2.5 (p = 0.003).

Table 4. Stratified Analysis of Pain Satisfaction Scores by Demographic Factors

Variable	Category	Group A: Para-cervical Block (Mean ± SD)	Group B: Nalbuphine (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Age (years)	<30 (n=38)	8.7 ± 1.6	6.3 ± 2.1	<0.001
	≥30 (n=22)	8.4 ± 1.8	5.9 ± 2.5	0.002
BMI (kg/m ²)	<25 (n=34)	8.8 ± 1.5	6.4 ± 2.0	<0.001
	≥25 (n=26)	8.3 ± 1.9	5.8 ± 2.4	0.001
Parity	<2 (n=37)	8.7 ± 1.6	6.2 ± 2.2	<0.001
	≥2 (n=23)	8.4 ± 1.8	6.0 ± 2.5	0.003

High satisfaction (VAS 8–10) was achieved by 21 patients (70.0%) in Group A compared to 10 patients (33.3%) in Group B. Moderate satisfaction (VAS 5–7) was reported in 26.7% of Group A versus 43.3% of Group B. Low satisfaction (VAS <5) was much more frequent in Group B (23.3%) compared to only 3.3% in Group A. This difference was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 8.75$, p = 0.003).

Table 5. Distribution of Pain Satisfaction Levels Among Study Participants

Pain Satisfaction Category (VAS)	Group A: Para-cervical Block (n=30)	Group B: Nalbuphine (n=30)	χ^2 value	p-value
High Satisfaction (VAS 8–10)	21 (70.0%)	10 (33.3%)	8.75	0.003
Moderate Satisfaction (VAS 5–7)	8 (26.7%)	13 (43.3%)		
Low Satisfaction (VAS <5)	1 (3.3%)	7 (23.3%)		

Discussion

The present randomized controlled trial compared the pain satisfaction scores of patients with first-trimester miscarriage undergoing manual vacuum aspiration under para-cervical block versus intravenous nalbuphine hydrochloride. We have established that para-cervical block gave a much higher pain satisfaction, intraoperative as well as one-hour after the procedure, than nalbuphine. Such findings underscore the effectiveness of local anesthesia as a method of patient comfort and acceptability of a procedure in the case of incomplete miscarriage. The average score of satisfaction with pains in the para-cervical block group was 8.6 \pm 1.7 during the surgery and 8.2 \pm 1.5 an hour after the surgery, in the nalbuphine group, respectively. The findings are congruent with the global literature which demonstrates that para-cervical block provides optimal locally measured pain management during uterine surgeries. An example is that in one of the studies in India, para-cervical block resulted in very low pain scores as opposed to intravenous sedation during suction evacuation [12]. On the same note, a trial carried out in Nigeria highlighted the idea that para-cervical block is a viable and affordable way of uterine evacuation in low-resource areas. Conversely, nalbuphine has been identified to be an effective systemic opioid analgesic which produces fewer respiratory depressant effects than morphine. Earlier research in Pakistan has conducted nalbuphine to investigate labor analgesia and minor gynecological operations showing average effectiveness [13]. Nevertheless, our research results show that nalbuphine used alone would not be effective enough to manage the pain during an MVA procedure, in which uterine manipulation is associated with major discomfort. Though, patients in the nalbuphine group had moderate satisfaction scores, a large percentage of the patients (23.3) had low satisfaction scores (VAS <5), which is not only clinically significant in terms of patient-centered care [14]. The stratified analysis in our study revealed that the superiority of para-cervical block was consistent across age, BMI, and parity subgroups, suggesting the robustness of the findings. This is especially crucial in the Pakistani population, where young, multiparous women frequently seek treatment for miscarriage and where patient comfort strongly

influences future health-seeking behavior. Both methods were well-received in terms of safety. No major adverse events occurred in either group [15]. Minor complications such as nausea were slightly more common with nalbuphine, while vasovagal reactions occurred in a few patients receiving para-cervical block. These side effects were self-limiting and did not affect overall outcomes. These observations are in line with prior studies reporting the relative safety of both techniques, though opioids tend to carry systemic side effects more frequently than local anesthesia [16,17]. A major strength of this trial was its randomized controlled design, which minimized selection bias. The use of standardized protocols and a single surgical team ensured consistency. However, there are some limitations. The study was conducted at a single tertiary care hospital, which may limit generalizability to rural or low-resource facilities. In addition, pain is inherently subjective, and despite the use of a visual analogue scale, individual perception of discomfort may vary. The relatively small sample size may also restrict the statistical power for detecting rare adverse events.

Conclusion

It is concluded that para-cervical block provides significantly higher pain satisfaction compared to intravenous nalbuphine hydrochloride in patients undergoing manual vacuum aspiration for first-trimester miscarriage. The block not only ensured superior intra-procedural and post-procedural pain control but was also associated with minimal side effects and better overall patient acceptance.

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